

IMPROVED MECHANISM OF THE DIGITAL QUALITY MANAGEMENT MODEL OF EDUCATION IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

Xaydarov Rustam

Doctoral student Institute for retraining and advanced training of
preschool education personnel and manager

e-mail: hayadrovrustam774@gmail.com

telephone: 998974553345

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Abstract: In this article we will consider issues related to the model of digital education management in preschool educational organizations. The main principles and tools of this model will be considered, as well as the advantages that it can bring in the educational process. We will also discuss possible challenges and aspects that should be taken into account when implementing this model. As a result, this article will provide an overview and understanding of how the improved mechanism of the digital quality management model of education can be implemented and used in preschool educational organizations..

Keywords: Digital management model, education, preschool educational organizations, quality of education, information and communication technologies, individualization of education, learning efficiency, accessibility of education, communication, data, analysis, advantages, challenges, implementation..

Introduction: In the modern world, digital technologies are playing an increasingly important role in various spheres of our lives. One of these areas is education, including preschool education. In this regard, there is a need to improve the quality management mechanisms of education in preschool educational organizations.

One of the innovative approaches to education quality management is the digital management model. This model is based on the use of information and communication technologies to collect, analyze and manage data on the quality of the educational process in preschool educational organizations (PEO).

The main advantage of the improved mechanism of the digital quality management model of education is the ability to obtain operational information about the effectiveness of the educational process. With the help of digital tools, it is possible to collect data on the achievements of children, the effectiveness of teachers, as well as feedback from parents. This allows the heads of preschool educational organizations to make informed decisions and make adjustments to the educational process to improve the quality of education.

In addition, the digital education quality management model provides an opportunity to automate processes such as planning annual, monthly, weekly thematic plans, assessing children's progress and monitoring the quality of education. This reduces the time spent by teachers and allows them to focus on developing individual approaches to each child.

Some of the key challenges in managing the quality of preschool education today may include:

1. Lack of funding and resources: Many preschool institutions are in a state of lack of financial and human resources to provide quality education.

2. Lack of qualified personnel: low wages and lack of opportunities for professional development can lead to the fact that preschool institutions have difficulties in attracting and retaining qualified teaching staff.

3. Low level of quality assessment: Some schools may have low standards and ineffective methods of assessing the quality of education, which may make it difficult to ensure a sufficiently high level of quality.

4. Lack of a competent management system: the lack of effective management methods can have a negative impact on the quality of education.

5. Lack of communication with families: unsuccessful communication between preschool institutions and families can lead to inefficiency of educational programs and lack of support from parents.

6. Many countries have not yet implemented digital technologies in preschool education

Due to the introduction of digital technologies, the didactic component of the educational environment of a preschool educational organization is supplemented by a media library, presentations, didactic materials, etc.

VII. Results: improved mechanism of digital quality management of education in preschool educational organizations

This allows teachers to conduct classes more interesting, fun and effective through the use of presentations and video materials using modern information technologies. Thus, an information and educational environment is created in educational organizations from preschool to school level.

Digitalization provides optimization of the information activity of the head of a preschool educational organization, since it allows you to process information quickly and in large volumes, store large volumes of information flows in an organized form.

Thus, the introduction of digital technologies in the field of preschool education management is an important stage in the informatization of an educational organization.

As a result of theoretical and practical research, we have developed an improved model of the quality management mechanism of preschool educational organizations in the conditions of digitalization (see Fig. 1).

A model of an improved mechanism for digital quality management of education in preschool educational institutions has been developed (Fig. 1). Based on modern education and needs, the goal has been determined. To achieve this goal, preschool educational organizations are tasked with studying the regulatory framework for quality management of education and the current state of digital management. At the same time, approaches and principles are defined. Pedagogical and organizational conditions for the development of the teaching quality management process have been identified in the digital environment. This is based on the need for an electronic platform for digital management of logistics, the Internet, and the quality of education. Instructions for using the platform and a textbook on information processing have been prepared. At the same time, a short-term training program on the use of the platform has been developed and courses have been organized in the regions. The learning process took a total of 24 hours.

In our opinion, with the introduction of digital technologies in the management of preschool educational organizations, the following indicators will increase:

- saving labor and time costs;
- awareness of the state of the managed system;
- efficiency of management decision-making;
- expediency and effectiveness of management decisions;
- optimization and automation of information processes;
- intellectual potential of the team.

At the technological stage, the initial, basic, and final stages of experimental work are determined. The directors of preschool educational organizations monitored the information processing processes. After completion of the monitoring process, the Director developed criteria for individual continuous analysis of information, self-management, ensuring openness of information and evaluation of cooperation, within which the director assessed the development of the digital environment using evaluation methods, evaluation criteria, evaluation levels and questionnaires. From the overall results of the assessment, it can be seen that the director of a preschool educational organization analyzes information, develops openness and cooperation.

The obtained practical result showed that the rapid development of digitalization of the educational process, its addition by means of information and communication technologies (ICT) has led to an improvement in the quality of education, on the one hand, and an increase in the volume of constantly growing management information in an educational organization.

This raises the problem of optimizing the management activities of the head of a preschool organization.

Digital technologies and developed programs make it possible to implement the "Information Vertical" of education quality management, providing managers with comprehensive information about all aspects of the organization's activities: education, training, management, well-being.

However, the introduction of an improved mechanism of the digital quality management model of education in preschool educational institutions requires not only technical training, but also ensuring data confidentiality, as well as training teachers to use new technologies. In conclusion, the improved mechanism of the digital education quality management model is an innovative approach that can significantly improve the educational process in preschool educational organizations. It allows you to get more accurate and timely information about the achievements of children, the effectiveness of teachers' work and contributes to improving the quality of education.

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